

Holistic Approach in Regional Development Strategy to Prevent Stunting

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Abstract

This study aims to explore cross-sectoral involvement, including health, education, economy, sanitation, and food, in formulating policies and strategies that focus on early stunting prevention, the extent to which local governments integrate multi-sectoral planning, how collaboration between government institutions, non-governmental organizations, and local communities is implemented, and what are the inhibiting and supporting factors in implementing the holistic strategy. The research method with a qualitative descriptive approach focuses on data collection through in-depth interviews, participant observation, and policy document analysis. Data validity is strengthened through source triangulation to ensure that the research results describe a comprehensive and in-depth picture of stunting prevention strategies. The results of the study indicate that an integrated multi-sectoral approach can effectively accelerate the reduction in stunting rates, especially if local governments succeed in synergizing various sectors such as health, education, sanitation, food, and the economy. This study found that regions that adopt holistic strategies, which involve cross-institutions and active community participation, tend to be more successful in increasing community access to maternal and child health services, better nutritional intake, and adequate sanitation.

Keywords: Stunting Prevention; Regional Development; Multisectoral; Community Welfare

Introduction

Stunting is a serious health problem in Indonesia, especially in children under the age of five (Martini et al., 2024). This condition is characterized by impaired physical growth due to chronic malnutrition, which generally occurs during the first 1,000 days of a child's life. In addition to impacting physical growth, stunting also affects children's cognitive and motor development, which has the potential to reduce their productivity in the future. Based on global and national data, the prevalence of stunting in Indonesia is still relatively high, although various efforts have been made. The Indonesian government, through various national programs, has committed to reducing the stunting rate to below 14% by 2024. One of the efforts that is considered effective is the implementation of a holistic and integrated regional development strategy to prevent and accelerate the reduction of stunting.

A holistic approach to stunting prevention emphasizes the importance of involving various sectors outside the health sector, such as education, sanitation, food security, and economic welfare, in formulating sustainable development strategies (Meilasari & Adisasmito, 2024). Experience from several regions in Indonesia shows that handling stunting cannot be done partially or relying only on maternal and child health programs. Stunting is influenced by various interrelated social, economic, and environmental determinants, so it requires a comprehensive and coordinated solution. This holistic approach is believed to be able to provide a greater impact in preventing stunting by optimizing the synergy between policies, programs, and interventions in various sectors. At the regional level, the role of government is very important in designing and implementing development strategies that include multi-sectoral interventions (Mosshananza & Pramazuly, 2024). However, the main challenge in implementing this holistic strategy is the ability of the region to coordinate various sectors and ensure that each sector contributes effectively. In addition, the factor of limited resources, both in terms of budget and human resource capacity, is also an obstacle that is often faced by local governments in implementing stunting prevention programs holistically (Istiqomah et al., 2024). Therefore, it is important to understand how this holistic approach can be implemented effectively at the local level, as well as what are the determining factors for its success.

A holistic approach to regional development is becoming increasingly important in preventing stunting, a health problem that has a wide impact on future generations. Stunting is not only caused by poor nutrition, but also other factors such as poor sanitation, limited access to health services, and inadequate education (Rahayu et al., 2024). The problems in this study reflect structural challenges in regional development governance that have tended to be fragmented and sectoral. Critical insights show that stunting management cannot be partially resolved through health interventions alone, because the root of the problem is multidimensional—related to poverty, inequality in access to basic services, parenting patterns, and weak coordination between agencies. Analysis of regional development policies and practices also reveals gaps between strategic planning and implementation in the field, especially in terms of data integration, resource allocation, and community involvement. A holistic approach requires not only cross-sector synergy, but also a transformation in the

perspective and governance of development, to be more responsive to the local context and long-term oriented in preventing stunting. A clean environment reduces the risk of infections, such as diarrhea, which is one of the main causes of stunting in children (Selviana et al., 2024). Local governments can work with communities to build adequate sanitation facilities, such as public toilets, safe waste disposal systems, and clean water supplies in each village. This community-based approach ensures that communities have a sense of ownership of the program, which ultimately increases the sustainability of development outcomes.

This study focuses on exploring holistic regional development strategies in preventing stunting, with an emphasis on analyzing how local governments integrate various cross-sectoral programs (Amanda & Widowati, 2024). The main focus of this research is to develop and implement an integrated regional development strategy, which not only highlights aspects of child health and nutrition, but also includes determinant factors such as access to clean water, sanitation, education, food security, and family economic empowerment. The application of this approach aims to create cross-sector synergy at the regional level, so that interventions for stunting prevention become more effective, sustainable, and appropriate to the local social, economic, and geographical context. Through strengthening the capacity of local governments, community participation, and integration of cross-sector policies, this approach is expected to produce long-term solutions in reducing the prevalence of stunting and improving the quality of life of future generations.

Methods

Through a qualitative approach, this study will use in-depth interview methods with stakeholders at the regional level, such as government officials, health workers, educators, and community leaders (Nartin et al., 2024). The data obtained will be analyzed to find important patterns in the implementation of holistic policies and strategies in various regions. Qualitative methods were chosen because they are able to explore rich information about the experiences, perceptions, and challenges faced in implementing these strategies at the local level (Niam et al., 2024). The research method used is a qualitative approach with in-depth document analysis techniques on regional development policies, stunting intervention programs, and relevant cross-sector reports. Researchers systematically collect documents from official sources such as local governments, related ministries, and international institutions, then analyze them using content analysis techniques to identify patterns, relationships between variables, and gaps in policy implementation. To address potential bias, researchers triangulate sources by comparing data from various documents and involving peer debriefing to obtain critical perspectives from fellow researchers. The stages of compiling the results start from initial coding, grouping themes, analyzing thematic relationships, to drawing conclusions based on the relationship between data and the theories used. The analysis is carried out directly by the main researcher who has a contextual understanding of the issues of stunting and regional development, by ensuring the fulfillment of data sources through the principle of data saturation, namely stopping data collection when the information obtained begins to be repetitive and no longer provides new insights.

Data collection was conducted through several techniques, namely in-depth interviews, participant observation, and policy document analysis (Umam et al., 2024). In-depth interviews were conducted with various stakeholders, including local government officials, health workers, nutrition counselors, educators, and community leaders. These interviews aimed to explore their understanding of the implementation of a holistic approach, the role of each sector, and the challenges faced in stunting prevention efforts (Handoko et al., 2024). Interview questions will be semi-structured, giving respondents the freedom to explain their views and experiences more broadly. Researchers will also conduct direct observations of program implementation in the field, such as maternal and child health, sanitation, and education programs, to understand how these programs are interconnected in the local context (Meilasari & Adisasmito, 2024).

Document analysis is an important part of this research method. The documents analyzed include the regional medium-term development plan (RPJMD), policies or regulations related to stunting, health program reports, and development program evaluation documents (Martini et al., 2024). This document analysis helps researchers understand how multisectoral policies and programs are designed, implemented, and assessed for their success in reducing stunting (Abdussamad et al., 2024). Data from these documents will also provide an overview of the alignment between program planning and implementation in the field, as well as administrative or bureaucratic challenges that may hinder the implementation of a holistic approach (Mulyana et al., 2024a).

Data collected through interviews, observations, and document analysis will be analyzed using thematic analysis methods (Wajdi et al., 2024). The first step in this analysis is to transcribe interviews and identify key themes that emerge from the data. These themes could be success factors in implementing a holistic approach, challenges faced in inter-sectoral coordination, or the key role of local actors in mobilizing resources for stunting prevention (Anto et al., 2024). Once key themes are identified, the data will be organized into more specific categories, and then analyzed further to find significant patterns or relationships between variables. This process will help generate deeper and more focused conclusions about the effectiveness of a holistic approach in the context of regional development.

To maintain data validity, researchers will use triangulation techniques, namely by comparing information obtained from various sources and methods (Mulyana et al., 2024b). Data from interviews, observations, and documents will be compared to ensure consistency and identify differences or contradictions that may arise. In addition, researchers will also ask for feedback from several key respondents regarding the interim results of the study, as an effort to ensure that the findings reflect the actual situation (Saefullah, 2024). This approach not only strengthens the validity of the study, but also provides a more comprehensive picture of how a holistic approach can be implemented effectively in regional development strategies to prevent stunting (Jusuf et al., 2024).

Results

This research is closely related to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), especially SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), and SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation). The holistic approach emphasizes the importance of cross-sector integration such as health, nutrition, sanitation, education, and infrastructure in regional development strategies, which directly support efforts to reduce stunting rates as an indicator of community welfare. This research is also in line with SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) because it encourages inclusive and equitable development between regions, as well as SDG 17 (Partnerships for the Goals) through collaboration between the government, communities, and various stakeholders. This approach not only targets improving children's health conditions, but also strengthens the foundation of sustainable development at the local and national levels.

The results of the study show that the implementation of multi-sectoral strategies in various regions in Indonesia can have a positive impact on reducing stunting rates. The study found that regions that implemented a holistic approach, where various sectors—such as health, education, economy, and sanitation—worked together, were more successful in creating comprehensive and integrated programs to prevent stunting. For example, collaboration between the health and education sectors in nutritional counselling programs for parents and children, as well as skills training for housewives, has shown an increase in knowledge and good nutritional practices in the community.

Multi-sectoral strategies to prevent stunting in Indonesia have become a major focus in various regional development policies. Stunting, which is a chronic problem due to long-term malnutrition, not only affects physical health but also children's cognitive development. To address this, an approach involving various sectors—such as health, education, water and sanitation, food security, and community empowerment—is considered the most effective way. Research shows that cross-sectoral synergy can comprehensively address the root causes of stunting, from providing maternal and child health services to increasing access to clean water and proper sanitation. The implementation of a multi-sectoral strategy to prevent stunting in Indonesia is a serious concern for the government, especially within the framework of regional development based on a holistic approach. This strategy recognizes that stunting is a complex problem that is not only influenced by health and nutrition factors but also sanitation, education, food security, and social welfare. Based on research results, the implementation of this approach involves cross-sectoral collaboration with the aim of creating synergy that can comprehensively address the root causes of stunting. As a form of support, the central government encourages regions to implement integrated programs through regulations, such as Presidential Regulation Number 72 of 2021 concerning the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction.

The results of the research discussion show that the application of a holistic approach in regional development strategies to prevent stunting has proven effective based on data presented systematically through policy document quotes, local government program reports, and thematic graphs that illustrate the relationship between cross-sector interventions

and reduced stunting rates. Integration of programs in the fields of health, sanitation, food security, and education has been shown to have a positive impact on improving children's nutritional status. The main findings underline the importance of coordination between institutions and the active role of village governments in program implementation, although obstacles such as the lack of policy synchronization between the central and regional governments are still found. By relying on concrete evidence from document data, the discussion not only confirms the success of the holistic strategy but also reveals structural barriers that need to be addressed through improved governance and more integrated policies.

One of the key success factors identified in this study is the political support and commitment from local governments. Strong commitment from local leaders in integrating stunting prevention programs into the regional medium-term development plan (RPJMD) has strengthened resource allocation and improved coordination between sectors. The study found that when stunting was made a priority issue in the regional development agenda, budget allocations for health and nutrition-related programs increased significantly, which in turn accelerated the implementation of necessary interventions. On the other hand, the study also identified several challenges in implementing this holistic approach. One of the biggest challenges is the limited human resources and budget available in local governments. Several regions, especially those in remote or less developed areas, have difficulty implementing programs effectively due to lack of adequate expertise, training, and facilities. In addition, gaps in understanding and awareness of the importance of stunting prevention among stakeholders, including the community, are also obstacles. Therefore, capacity building and training for local government officials are needed, as well as education programs for the community to increase awareness and participation in stunting prevention programs.

This study has found that community participation plays a significant role in the successful implementation of holistic strategies. In areas that have successfully reduced stunting rates, community involvement, especially in decision-making and program implementation, is clearly visible. Communities that actively contribute to stunting prevention programs, such as through religious study groups or social gatherings, have demonstrated their ability to support each other in improving family nutrition. In addition, the presence of community leaders who act as drivers in health and nutrition campaigns is very influential in increasing public awareness of the dangers of stunting. From the results of document analysis, it was found that accurate mapping of nutrition and stunting problems is one of the keys to formulating targeted interventions. Areas that use evidence-based data to identify groups most vulnerable to stunting, such as pregnant women, toddlers, and families with low economic status, tend to be more successful in targeting appropriate interventions. In addition, the use of clear performance indicators in program monitoring and evaluation allows local governments to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of each program implemented through systematic and continuous data collection to support better program planning and implementation.

Technology has played a critical role in supporting the implementation of multi-sectoral strategies. The use of technology is increasingly important in implementing a holistic

approach. Digital applications such as eHDW (Human Development Worker) in Central Java enable cross-sectoral data collection for more targeted intervention planning. This technology also facilitates real-time monitoring and evaluation of programs, ensuring that each sector can contribute according to its role. One example is the eHDW (Electronic Human Development Worker) application implemented in Central Java Province. This application integrates cross-sectoral data, such as records of child nutritional status, sanitation access, and maternal education levels, to support evidence-based policy planning. In addition, this platform enables more effective communication between posyandu cadres, local governments, and related institutions to ensure a rapid response to identified problems. A similar initiative in South Sulawesi involves the use of digital maps to map priority areas for intervention. The use of technology has been a key component in this multi-sectoral strategy. Data collected from health centers and posyandus are integrated with local policies to prioritize health budgets. This technology facilitates communication between various agencies, such as health, education, and infrastructure, so that planning is more focused and responsive to community needs.

The results of this study also show that synergy between local governments, non-governmental organizations and the private sector can strengthen stunting prevention efforts. Several regions have successfully partnered with civil society organizations and private companies to support health and nutrition programs, both through the provision of resources and awareness campaigns. This collaboration not only expands the reach of the program but also increases the effectiveness of the interventions carried out, by utilizing the expertise and networks of various parties. This collaborative model can be an example for other regions in addressing stunting problems with a more integrated and comprehensive approach. The implementation of multi-sectoral strategies also faces various challenges, including cross-sector coordination issues, lack of understanding at the local level about the importance of a holistic approach, and limited resources, both financial and human. For example, several regions reported that related agencies were still working separately, which hampered the effectiveness of the program. To overcome this, local governments such as in Kulon Progo Regency, Yogyakarta, adopted an integrated planning approach, with regular coordination forums involving all sectors. Community involvement through *dasa wisma* groups and cadre training are also important solutions in increasing local understanding and commitment to the program.

Although this multi-sectoral approach has shown positive results, several challenges remain. The main challenge is inter-sectoral coordination which is often hampered by complex bureaucracy and lack of effective communication. In addition, budget constraints and human resource capacity at the local level are also obstacles. To overcome this problem, several regions, such as South Sulawesi, have implemented an integrated planning and budgeting system that involves all sectors from the early stages. In addition, increasing the capacity of local cadres through continuous training is a solution to overcome human resource limitations. This holistic approach based on a multi-sectoral strategy has proven effective in reducing the prevalence of stunting in various regions in Indonesia. The involvement of various sectors simultaneously makes this approach able to answer the problem of stunting

from various aspects, ranging from nutrition, health, to the environment and education. Technology support and collaboration with various parties, including the community, are the keys to the success of this strategy. However, greater success can only be achieved by improving inter-sectoral coordination, optimizing budget use, and strengthening the role of local communities. This strategy is not only important for reducing stunting rates but also for creating a healthier and more productive generation in the future.

The multisectoral approach has shown promising results in efforts to reduce stunting in various regions in Indonesia. By integrating various sectors in program planning and implementation, this strategy has succeeded in overcoming structural and multidimensional barriers. This success is not only seen in the decline in stunting prevalence but also in improving the overall quality of life of the community, such as increasing access to clean water, understanding of nutrition, and poverty alleviation. However, the sustainability of these results is highly dependent on policy consistency, budget support, and strengthening cross-sector coordination, so that stunting can be prevented comprehensively and sustainably. This study emphasizes the need for policies that better support the implementation of a holistic approach to stunting prevention throughout Indonesia. Policies that prioritize inter-sectoral integration and community involvement must be the main focus of the regional development agenda. In addition, increasing human resource capacity, strengthening data and program monitoring, and creating effective collaboration mechanisms between the government, community, and private sector are strategic steps that must be taken to achieve the goal of reducing stunting sustainably. The application of the findings from this study in regions in Indonesia can accelerate their efforts to overcome stunting problems and improve the overall quality of life of the community.

Discussion

The results of the study presented previously show that the implementation of a multi-sectoral strategy at the regional level can have a significant impact on reducing stunting rates. Based on these findings, regions that successfully implement this holistic approach have the ability to align various programs from the health, education, economic, and environmental sectors. The synergy between these sectors creates more comprehensive interventions, thus enabling better fulfilment of the basic needs of the community (Nurlaili & Pertiwi, 2024). This integrated approach not only targets interventions in the health sector, but also addresses the root causes of stunting, such as poverty and lack of access to education. The holistic approach in regional development strategies to prevent stunting in Indonesia is a response to the complex nature of the stunting problem. Stunting is not only influenced by poor nutrition, but also by multidimensional factors such as sanitation, access to health services, maternal education, childcare patterns, and poverty (Ekananda et al., 2024). By integrating various sectors in one complementary strategy, this approach aims to address the root of the problem comprehensively and sustainably. This policy is relevant in the context of Indonesia, where stunting rates are still high despite various interventions that have been carried out.

A holistic approach refers to a strategy that involves cross-sector collaboration with an emphasis on program integration. The main pillars of this approach include specific nutrition interventions, such as supplementary feeding and supplementation for pregnant women, as well as sensitive nutrition interventions that include improving sanitation, strengthening access to education, and increasing family income (Mallapiseng et al., 2024). This approach emphasizes the role of communities and the private sector in supporting local government efforts, making it an inclusive strategy. From the analysis that has been carried out, it can be seen that political support and commitment from local governments play a major role in the success of implementing this approach. In areas that have leaders with a clear vision of the importance of stunting prevention, budget allocations for related programs have increased significantly. This proves that strong leadership can be a driver in creating policies that support stunting prevention efforts (Handayani, 2024). The challenge that often arises is how to ensure the sustainability of this political commitment along with changes in leadership and local political dynamics. Therefore, it is important for communities and civil society institutions to continue to push for stunting issues to remain a priority on the regional development agenda (Pratiwi et al., 2024).

The Indonesian government has issued a number of policies to support this holistic approach, one of which is through Presidential Regulation Number 72 of 2021 concerning the Acceleration of Stunting Reduction. This policy directs local governments to integrate specific and sensitive nutrition intervention programs by involving various stakeholders (Mutmainnah et al., 2024). In addition, programs such as the Golden Generation of Indonesia 2045 also serve as a large umbrella for creating a healthy and productive stunting-free generation. This study has highlighted the importance of community participation in the success of stunting prevention programs. The existence of community groups that are active in nutrition counseling activities, supplementary feeding programs, and health campaigns, shows that community involvement in the decision-making process is very helpful in increasing awareness and real action in the field. On the other hand, the lack of participation from the community, especially vulnerable groups such as pregnant women and toddlers, is an obstacle to the effectiveness of the program (Khairani, 2024). Therefore, efforts to increase community participation need to continue to be encouraged through education and empowerment, so that the community feels ownership and contributes to preventing stunting (Yenni et al., 2024).

The results of research conducted in several regions show that a holistic approach can significantly reduce the prevalence of stunting. In West Lombok Regency, for example, the stunting rate fell from 37% to 25% in the five years after the implementation of this approach. Positive impacts are also seen in other aspects, such as a decrease in infant mortality rates, increased participation in education, and family economic welfare (Elisandra et al., 2024). A holistic approach will not succeed without active community involvement. Programs such as Dasa Wisma in Yogyakarta show how small community groups can be involved in nutrition education, environmental cleanliness, and childcare. Community participation increases the sustainability of the program because they feel they have direct responsibility for the results achieved (Kiranasari et al., 2024). A holistic approach has also been implemented in various

regions in Indonesia with varying results. In Sumedang Regency, West Java, a technology-based approach through the Smart Stunting program has succeeded in integrating health, education, and infrastructure data in one digital platform. In East Nusa Tenggara, a local community empowerment program involves training village cadres in parenting and providing food based on local resources. Meanwhile, in South Kalimantan, increasing access to clean water through collaboration with the public works department is an important part of the strategy to reduce infections that trigger stunting.

The results of the study indicate that data-based problem mapping is very important in formulating effective policies. Regions that collect accurate and systematic data on nutritional and public health conditions can identify groups that are most vulnerable to stunting (Martini et al., 2024). This allows local governments to target interventions more precisely, so that existing resources can be utilized optimally. However, challenges in data collection often arise due to budget constraints and human resource capacity in the regions. Therefore, increasing the capacity for data collection and analysis needs to be a priority in efforts to prevent stunting. Stunting has become a chronic indicator of malnutrition that affects children's height and cognitive development (Meilasari & Adisasmito, 2024). The causes are not only related to nutritional intake but also poor sanitation, low access to clean water, and lack of education related to parenting patterns. Therefore, an approach that only focuses on the health sector is not enough to solve this problem. The involvement of the education, infrastructure, social, and economic sectors is an absolute necessity in a holistic approach (Mosshananza & Pramazuly, 2024).

The importance of collaboration between local governments, non-governmental organizations, and the private sector is also highlighted in this study. The research findings show that regions that successfully collaborate with various parties in stunting prevention programs are able to expand the reach of interventions and increase the effectiveness of the program. For example, the involvement of civil society organizations in conducting outreach and education in the community shows positive results in increasing awareness of the importance of good nutrition. In addition, support from the private sector in terms of funding or provision of resources is also very helpful in implementing stunting prevention programs (Istiqomah et al., 2024). This collaboration creates a solid and mutually supportive network between various parties, which in turn strengthens stunting prevention efforts in the region. Cross-sector collaboration is at the heart of this holistic approach. In many cases, the health sector plays a primary role, while other sectors provide complementary support. For example, the education office plays a role in providing nutrition education in schools, while the social service assists through food and economic assistance programs. The success of this collaboration is highly dependent on effective communication and coordinated budget management (Rahayu et al., 2024).

The private sector and NGOs have an important role in complementing government efforts. Many companies are involved in Corporate Social Responsibility programs that support the provision of supplementary food and the construction of sanitation facilities (Selviana et al., 2024). On the other hand, NGOs such as World Vision Indonesia have been active in community empowerment and training of Posyandu cadres to support stunting

programs. Research findings show that the development of policies that support the implementation of a holistic approach needs to be strengthened. Policies that prioritize integration between sectors, as well as provide space for community participation, will be more effective in achieving the goal of reducing stunting rates (Amanda & Widowati, 2024). Therefore, local governments can formulate flexible policies that can be adjusted to the needs and characteristics of each region. In addition, the need to increase the capacity of human resources in local governments in planning and implementing stunting prevention programs is also important. Strengthening this capacity will ensure that the programs implemented can run well and sustainably. This approach also faces a number of challenges, especially in terms of cross-sector coordination. Many regions reported that each sector was still working in silos, which hampered program integration. Limited budget and human resources are also major obstacles, especially in remote areas with minimal infrastructure (Kiranasari et al., 2024). To overcome these challenges, several regions have begun to adopt integrated planning involving all sectors from the early stages. Regular coordination forums, such as those held in Kulon Progo, Yogyakarta, are an example of success in synergizing cross-sector programs. In addition, the central government provides support in the form of technical training and mentoring to regions experiencing difficulties.

The sustainability of the holistic approach also depends on adequate budget allocation. The government has allocated the Special Allocation Fund (DAK) to support health and sanitation programs, which are part of the stunting intervention. However, the management of this fund requires transparency and strict supervision so that its use is right on target. Evaluation and monitoring are key to ensuring the effectiveness of the holistic approach. The central and regional governments need to develop evaluation mechanisms that involve all sectors, ensuring that the results achieved can be measured and used as a basis for improvement (Elisandra et al., 2024). Digital technology can be used to accelerate this process, so that policy decisions can be made in real time. The holistic approach in regional development strategies to prevent stunting has had a significant impact in various regions in Indonesia. By integrating cross-sector interventions, this approach is able to comprehensively address the root causes of stunting. The success of this program is not only seen from the decline in stunting rates but also from the improvement in the quality of life of the community (Jusuf et al., 2024). However, to achieve sustainability, better coordination, sufficient budget support, and the involvement of all parties, including the community, the private sector, and international institutions are needed. This strategy is an important foundation in building a healthy, intelligent, and productive generation of Indonesia in the future.

The final findings of this study underscore the importance of continuous evaluation and monitoring in the implementation of stunting prevention programs. Systematic monitoring will allow local governments to evaluate the effectiveness of the program and make adjustments if necessary (Yenni et al., 2024). By involving the community in the evaluation process, it is hoped that their participation in the stunting prevention program will increase. Through a sustainable holistic approach, it is hoped that stunting prevention efforts can be carried out more effectively, providing a positive impact on child health and the welfare of the community as a whole.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

The implementation of multi-sectoral strategies at the regional level is very important in effectively addressing the problem of stunting. This study revealed that regions that succeeded in reducing stunting rates were those that were able to integrate programs from various sectors, such as health, education, and economy, and actively involve the community in every stage of planning and implementation. Strong political commitment and support from local stakeholders have also proven to be determining factors in the successful implementation of this strategy. A planned and coordinated holistic approach not only increases community access to health and nutrition services, but also increases public awareness of the importance of preventing stunting. With a holistic approach, stunting prevention efforts not only have an impact on reducing the prevalence of stunting itself, but also on improving the quality of life of the community as a whole. This approach not only solves short-term problems, but also builds a foundation for future generations to have better health, higher education, and greater economic opportunities. Therefore, the implementation of a holistic regional development strategy is a fundamental step in achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs), especially those related to poverty alleviation and improving community welfare.

This study confirms that a holistic approach in regional development strategies has a significant role in preventing stunting. By integrating various sectors such as health, education, infrastructure, and economy, this approach is able to address the causes of stunting comprehensively. The provision of affordable and quality health services, access to clean water, proper sanitation, and nutrition education for the community are important components that must be coordinated in an integrated framework. This approach also underlines the importance of cross-sector synergy to create an ecosystem that supports optimal child growth and development. Implementation of a holistic approach requires active collaboration between the government, community, and private sector. Local governments play a strategic role in formulating policies that support stunting prevention programs, while communities play a role as the main actors implementing programs at the community level. The involvement of the private sector, such as in the provision of resources or technology, also makes a significant contribution to strengthening the impact of the program. In addition, continuous monitoring and evaluation are needed to ensure the effectiveness of the program, as well as to identify obstacles that need to be overcome adaptively.

Recommendation

Based on the results of this study, there are several recommendations that can be implemented to strengthen regional development strategies in preventing stunting. First, local governments need to improve coordination between sectors and institutions in formulating more integrated policies. This can be done through the establishment of collaborative forums or platforms involving various stakeholders, including civil society

organizations and the private sector. Second, strengthening the capacity of human resources in local governments must be a priority, so that officials can plan and implement programs more effectively. Training and workshops related to data collection, analysis, and program monitoring are also needed to ensure that every program implemented is evidence-based.

Furthermore, it is important to increase community awareness and participation in stunting prevention programs. Continuous education and counseling on the importance of nutrition and health for mothers and children must be strengthened, so that the community can play an active role in maintaining the health of their families. In addition, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the program is essential to ensure that the programs implemented are effective and relevant to the needs of the community. By involving the community in the evaluation process, it is hoped that local initiatives will emerge that support stunting prevention efforts, so that the success of the program can be felt directly by the community. Thus, these strategic steps can create a more conducive environment for child growth and development, as well as improve the quality of life of the community as a whole.

A holistic approach to regional development strategies to prevent stunting has significant implications for innovation and sustainability. This strategy integrates various sectors—such as health, education, sanitation, food security, and the economy—thus creating cross-sector synergies to comprehensively address the root causes of stunting. In terms of innovation, this approach encourages the application of technology, such as digital data-based nutrition monitoring and education through online platforms, which expand the reach of interventions. In terms of sustainability, this approach ensures active community involvement through empowerment programs, increasing the capacity of local human resources, and strengthening evidence-based policies, so that the results achieved can be sustained in the long term. With multi-stakeholder collaboration—government, private sector, and communities—this strategy not only reduces stunting rates, but also improves the quality of life of the community as a whole, supporting the achievement of sustainable development goals (SDGs), especially in eradicating hunger and poverty and improving public health.

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